

THE IMAGE OF THE MODERN TEACHER, TEACHER SPEECH CULTURE AND MODERN EDUCATIONAL METHODS AND THE METHODOLOGY OF USING THEM

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Abstract. *Methodological training and creativity of the teacher, image is the moral essence of the person and the proportion of appearance according to it in problematic situations in the formation of the speech culture of the teacher, modern education.*

Keywords: *modern teacher, communicative culture, imageology, professional image, teaching method, positive image.*

The most important thing in any education and upbringing is the teacher, his world of thought.

A. Disterweg

INTRODUCTION

Methodological preparation and creativity of the teacher - The necessary social skills of the teacher should include: Self-expression; Social communication with other people; Work tirelessly on oneself; the ability to assess the situation and solve problems; Organization, creative approach; management skills.

The key to education is speech, the key to education is behavior.

A person who has speech behavioral culture can be called a perfect person. Teacher speech should include Correct speech, Pure speech, Terms, Logic, Expressiveness. Communicativeness in psychology means "developing a new attitude, solution, method, theory, or new product of some kind of communication". Communication (lat. komunikatio — message, communication) is the transmission of a message or speech content through language. Competence (derived from the Latin word "competo", which means "I reach, I am suitable") means a specific set of knowledge, skills, and abilities acquired by a person.

Communicative competence - the acquisition of complex communication skills and abilities, the formation of sufficient skills in new social structures, knowledge of cultural norms and limitations in communication, knowledge of customs, traditions and etiquette, good behavior, characteristic of the national mentality and expressed within the profession orientation to communicative means. Communicative culture is a collection of skills, abilities and personal communicative qualities that enable individuals to know the laws of communication, use its tools in various life and work conditions. Communicative culture is a part of the basic culture of a person, which ensures his readiness for self-determination in life, establishes a harmonious relationship with the surrounding reality and within himself. Popular scientific treatises of E. Begmatov on speech culture: "Speech culture and literary norm" (1973); "The skill of public speaking" (1979); "The rare wealth of the orator" (1980); "The Culture of Literary Pronunciation" (1982); "Gem of speech" (1984).

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

There are 2 ways to influence people. "Confidence method" and "Ignition method". The last one is more effective. Blaise Pascal's image of a modern teacher is a set of qualities and virtues that shape the public's positive attitude towards him. The translation of the word "image" from English language into Uzbek language means "appearance", "image", "figure", "symbol". Imageology is the art and science of pleasing people. Imageology is a call to every person to be attractive and share light with people. Imageology is a technology of influence. The corporate image affects your personal image, and conversely, your image directly affects the organization's image. What does the image look like? - appearance; cultural dress; traditions and customs; activities and efforts; human morality; behavior; goals; character; friends and relations... Image is not only an image, but also a set of attitudes and thoughts about it. Image is the moral essence of a person and the proportion of appearance in accordance with it. Image is not a psychological tool to achieve a certain goal. The image is one there should be no repeated success. It is a continuous result and effect should be given. Why do you need an image? 92% of the image of a person's appearance and image is formed. "80-20" formula: 80-effective visual feature, 20-effective speech effect. Imaging studies attract the attention of specialists in many fields. Among them are psychologists, sociologists, political scientists, marketers, philosophers, teachers, PR and advertising specialists. The tasks of the image: teach people the way of life, encourage them to live actively, work on themselves and improve their skills; creates personal pride, self-confidence and optimism; harmonizes relations between people, conflicts and contradictions are eliminated; performs a psychotherapeutic task. The main task of the image is to respond to the wishes of other people. Every person has several images: professional, social, family and personal image. The composition of the coach's image: professional skills, appearance and individual characteristics. Characteristics necessary for a professional image: Ability to work; Inclination and fearlessness to show off; Ability to resolve conflict situations; Ability to establish cooperation with everyone; Communicability, that is, the ability to communicate in a broad sense; Being able to treat others kindly, openly, sincerely, correctly, equally, politely; Being able to convince others, being able to follow oneself, being able to influence others; Ability to quickly adapt to different conditions, adaptability to people and conditions; Optimism, full confidence in the correctness of one's goals. Verbal effect - the feet are in a folded position, the hands move in moderation, the voice is not too high or vice versa, Studying without sitting, etc. The image is related to the personal and professional qualities of the pedagogue - facial expressions (meaningful movements of facial muscles); gesture; voice timbre (specific qualities of sound) and strength; outerwear culture; manner of dealing; includes components such as interests, values, such as taking a specific step. Psychologists say that every body movement, facial expression conveys non-verbal information about a person to the second person, which helps to feel his mood, how inclined he is to communicate. Considering that the teacher is the role model in the lesson, it is not difficult to understand how important his actions and facial expressions are.

Mimicry - meaningful movements of facial muscles. The teacher must know how to manage non-verbal behavior in moderation. Appearance is the main component of the image. By expressing the emotions you feel, you can reach your intended audience of readers. Appearance is a unique business card of a person. A sincere look increases the effectiveness of the words a person says by 25%. With DRESS a person not only protects from heat and cold, but is also a sign of his culture. "65+35 FORMULA" - 35% of the information about our inner world, who we are, is

gained through our speech, the rest, 65 percent, we convey through our actions. Useful tips: 1. It is better to wear bright colored suits during the day and dark ones at night. 2. Always keep one suit neat and clean. 3. Do not tirelessly chase after fashion. It is better to wear simple clothes rather than trendy clothes. The main rule to follow when choosing clothes is to match the season and environment. The task of clothes is not only to protect a person from heat and cold, but also to attract. A person is judged by his clothes. Neat and elegant clothes indicate a person's demanding work and inner modesty. I wish you success in shaping your image! In order to make a good impression on students, it is necessary to pay attention to appearance, voice and content of speech. A positive image affects the effectiveness of the teacher's education. The teacher's image begins to form from the first meeting. Organization: Simple things like furniture arrangement, work space decoration, pen and glasses case also tell about us. When decorating the room, the teacher should choose a color that is soothing and does not interfere with children's learning. It is necessary not to leave out such things as the lighting of the room and the correct location of the teacher's desk. Do you consider yourself to be a well-rounded pedagogue? The classroom plays an important role in creating a healthy environment for children to develop. Its hygienic, aesthetic response to modern requirements has a positive effect on the quality of education.

TEACHING IS NOT A PROFESSION, TEACHING IS A WAY OF LIFE!

It can be seen that the times require the school teacher to work on his image. However, if we follow all the elements of the image, sometimes we do not get the desired result. Maybe we lack pedagogical skills? Therefore, in order to be a master of his profession, a teacher should not only have deep and perfect knowledge of his subject, but should also cultivate the following pedagogical qualities: devotion to his profession; knowledge of pedagogy and psychology; planning the educational process; work on yourself; love for children; innovation in the educational environment; Knowledge of ICT and foreign languages; self-confidence; tolerance. First you work for the image, then the image works for you! We have a very rich and beautiful language. There is no thought, feeling, or situation that cannot be expressed in this language. Abdullah Qahhor

Problematic situations in the formation of teacher's speech culture - 3 important qualities for intellectuals: Communication culture and eloquence; 2. Harmony of thought and language, standard of voice; 3. Internal culture. What are 3 mistakes in speech culture? - Do not make eye contact. Hide your hands. Not working with the audience. The main characteristics of speech: correctness of speech (compliance with language standards); Clarity of speech (consistency between things and events between nature and society); The logic of the speech (there is a consistent connection between the sentences); Purity of speech (without dialectism, barbarism); Effectiveness of speech. "Identifying and confirming the problem" - Lack of speaking skills - Lack of oral communication skills; Not fully following the standards of literary language; Not working on yourself; spending time on the Internet and social networks; Not reading works of art. Speaking is a privilege. You have the ability to influence people and even change their lives. The main weapon of a teacher is his eloquence: If the teacher's eloquence is weak and low, he will not be able to instill his knowledge of his subject in the minds of his students. Both the teacher and the student suffer in the middle. If the teacher is an eloquent, he directs all that he knows into the hearts of the students and pupils, and he and the listeners enjoy it. 10 rules of expressive speech:

1. Know the essence of the subject deeply;
2. Treat the student with respect;

3. Emphasize the word logically, pause before speaking and acquire the skills of gestures;
4. Use simple and fluent words in speech;
5. Speak clearly and in a voice that everyone can hear;
6. Do not use unnecessary words that have come out of a mold and have settled in the language;
7. Use a personal account;
8. Avoid speaking in slang and mixing languages;
9. Do not deceive the reader, do not misrepresent the truth;
10. Do not forget that the tone of your speech affects the emotional state of the students.

VOICE - the technical support of teacher's speech.

Teacher's voice increases the importance of the meaning of the speech and affects its image. The voice is sonorous, beautiful, powerful, pleasant, gentle, exciting. The voice is rough, hoarse, weak, unattractive, annoying. Think about what kind of voice you have. The first meeting is very important in how a person makes an impression on the interlocutor. According to sociological data, 9% of the impression of a person is the content of the conversation, 37% is the voice and 54 percent is based on appearance.

Tone is the dress of words and sentences. V.G. Belinsky says: "It's not about the words, it's about how the words are pronounced in the tone." The art of public speaking is a very broad concept that cannot be studied in a single mold.

A person gets to know the world with his mind through scientific literature, feels the world with his heart through fiction literature, and conveys it to other people through the art of speaking. Eloquence and spirituality are of great importance in the work of teachers, but it cannot be formed without books and knowledge. Because there is no science without spirituality, so there is no spirituality and eloquence without science.

Our wish: May your book of life be enriched with pages of happiness decorated with beautiful speech!

Conclusion

The object of pedagogy is a person formed in the process of educational activities and relationships. The subject of pedagogy is educational actions and relationships that affect human development. Method - (greek. "metodos"—a way of knowing or research, theory, doctrine)—guidelines, set of ways for practical and theoretical mastering, learning, knowing reality, a way of creating and justifying knowledge. Teaching method is a method of joint learning activity of the teacher and the student. Classification of educational methods: according to the history of development - Traditional; Unconventional; Modern; Innovative. According to the relationship between the teacher and the student: Interactive; Interpassive.

According to sources of learning: oral methods (lectures, books, conversations, discussions); written; visual methods (video materials, events, visual aids); practical methods (practical training, creative works, courses and dissertations); according to the method of supervision of educational activities: direct and indirect methods of leadership; according to didactic goals: methods of organizing students' activities; methods of stimulating activity, methods of checking and evaluating results, methods of rest; according to the nature of cognitive activity, the level of independence and creativity of students: reproductive (explanatory and illustrative, problematic presentation, reproductive) and effective (partial search and research).

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